

Measurement, Analysis, and Transmission of Sensor Data Using an STM32 Microcontroller and LoRa Communication

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Abkürzungen und Symbole

ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter
ESP_32	Microcontroller with integrated Wi-Fi and Bluetooth
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transform
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
LoRa	Long Range wireless communication technology for LPWAN
NN	Neural Network
RMS	Root Mean Square
TTN	The Things Network (LoRaWAN-Backend)
UART	Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
STM_32	Mikrocontroller family von STMicroelectronics

1. Introduction and Objectives

As part of the *Sensorsystems* module, an embedded measurement system is developed to monitor the electrical current consumption of a connected device and to determine its current operating state based on the measured signal. The extracted information is subsequently transmitted to an external backend via an energy-efficient wireless communication link.

A hot air blower with multiple operating modes is used as an exemplary load. The objective is to reliably distinguish between the operating states *off*, *fan operation without heating element*, and *fan operation with heating element* based solely on the measured current signal. The classification is performed directly on a resource-constrained microcontroller; only the resulting class information is transmitted via LoRaWAN.

This task entails several technical requirements:

- current measurement with sufficient bandwidth and galvanic isolation,
- efficient feature extraction and classification on a microcontroller with limited computational resources,
- robust wireless transmission at low data rates and minimal payload size, and
- reproducible signal conditioning through appropriate analog preprocessing.

The implemented solution consists of a complete measurement, signal processing, and classification pipeline deployed on an ESP32 microcontroller, followed by the transmission of the classification result to a LoRaWAN backend.

Component / Tool	Function within the System
ESP32 Dev Kit	Central control unit for data acquisition, signal processing, classification, and LoRa communication
Current Sensor (Grove Electricity Sensor)	Galvanically isolated acquisition of the load current signal
Offset and Amplifier Circuit	Adaptation of the sensor signal to the ADC input range through offset shifting and amplification
LoRa Radio Module (UART Interface)	Wireless transmission of the classification result to the backend
Arduino Toolchain	Compilation and flashing of the firmware onto the ESP32
Julia	Offline data analysis, Goertzel-based spectral evaluation, and neural network training
The Things Network (TTN)	Reception, processing, and visualization of LoRa uplink messages
Oscilloscope / Multimeter	Verification of offset, amplification, and signal waveform

Table 1.1: Tools and components used

2. System Concept

The developed sensor system is designed as an embedded measurement and classification unit that locally acquires electrical current signals, processes them, and wirelessly transmits the resulting information to a backend system. Figure 2.1 illustrates the overall system architecture and the interconnection of the individual functional blocks.

An **ESP32 microcontroller** is used as the central processing unit of the system. Initially, the use of a microcontroller from the **STM32 family** was planned. However, due to practical limitations encountered during programming and commissioning, the ESP32 was selected instead. The ESP32 fully meets the functional requirements of the system and provides sufficient computational resources for signal processing and classification tasks.

Current measurement is performed using a **galvanically isolated current sensor**, which captures the load current of the connected device via inductive voltage coupling. The sensor provides an alternating voltage output whose amplitude is proportional to the flowing current. For the investigated load, the sensor output voltage is in the range of a few hundred millivolts RMS.

Since the analog-to-digital converter (ADC) of the ESP32 can only process direct voltages in the range of 0 V to 3.3 V, the sensor signal is conditioned in the analog domain prior to digitization. This is achieved by means of an **offset and amplification stage**, which shifts the alternating signal to a suitable DC level while simultaneously amplifying it. This signal conditioning ensures optimal utilization of the available ADC input range.

All digital processing of the measured data is performed locally on the microcontroller. This includes discrete-time sampling of the signal, feature extraction, and subsequent classification of the operating state. Communication with the LoRa radio module is realized via a **serial UART interface**, using one of the available hardware UARTs of the ESP32. The radio module handles network joining and transmits the classification result to a LoRaWAN gateway.

The backend system is based on **The Things Network (TTN)** and is exclusively responsible for receiving and decoding the transmitted data. All signal processing and classification steps are carried out entirely on the embedded system. Consequently, the system boundaries are defined between the sensor and the analog-to-digital converter on one side, and between the microcontroller and the LoRaWAN gateway on the other.

This architectural approach was deliberately chosen, as local data processing significantly reduces the amount of data to be transmitted and thus minimizes the LoRaWAN payload size. At the same time, the computational load on the backend is kept low, while the ESP32 provides sufficient resources to efficiently execute the applied signal processing and classification methods.

Figure 2.1: Block diagram of the developed system

3. Implementation

3.1 Overview of the Implementation

The practical realization of the sensor system comprises all processing steps from the electrical acquisition of the current signal to the wireless transmission of the classification result. Both analog and digital processing stages are combined and integrated into a cohesive embedded system.

A central element of the implementation is the analog signal conditioning of the output provided by the current sensor, ensuring compatibility with the analog-to-digital converter of the microcontroller. Based on this conditioned signal, digital signal processing and operational state classification are performed directly on the ESP32. In addition, the measurement data are evaluated offline and used for model development before the trained parameters are embedded into the firmware.

The objective of the implementation is a robust and reproducible processing chain in which the complete signal analysis and classification are executed locally on the embedded system. Only highly condensed result data are transmitted via the LoRaWAN interface, minimizing communication overhead and making the system suitable for energy-efficient applications.

3.2 Hardware Architecture and Analog Signal Conditioning

The electrical measurement chain is based on a galvanically isolated current sensor that captures the load current of the connected appliance via voltage induction. The sensor provides a low-level alternating output voltage whose amplitude is proportional to the flowing current. In the considered application scenario, this voltage typically lies in the range of a few hundred millivolts RMS.

Analog signal conditioning is realized by a combined offset and amplification stage, as illustrated in Figure 3.1. A voltage divider generates a constant offset voltage of approximately 1.8 V from the microcontroller supply voltage, thereby shifting the negative half-wave of the alternating signal into the permissible input range of the analog-to-digital converter.

In addition, the sensor signal is amplified to utilize the available dynamic range of the ADC as efficiently as possible. The selected gain of approximately 3.8 represents a suitable compromise between signal resolution and headroom against saturation. This conditioning enables accurate digitization of the current signal.

The conditioned signal is routed to the ADC of the ESP32 via a dedicated analog input channel. Communication with the LoRa radio module is established through a serial UART interface, using one of the available hardware UARTs of the microcontroller. Power for both the microcontroller and the radio module is supplied via the USB port of the development board, eliminating the need for an additional external power source.

Figure 3.1: Schematic of the current sensor, offset and amplifier stage, and connection to the LoRa module and ESP32

3.3 Firmware Implementation on the ESP32

The firmware running on the ESP32 enables the complete digital processing chain from data acquisition to the transmission of the classification result. All time-critical signal processing and classification steps are executed locally on the microcontroller, eliminating the need for continuous transmission of raw measurement data.

Data Acquisition

The current signal is acquired via the analog-to-digital converter (ADC) of the ESP32. For each measurement cycle, 2000 ADC samples are recorded using a sampling interval of approximately 100 μ s. Based on the measurement timestamps, the effective sampling rate is determined dynamically and is approximately 3 kHz on average. This dynamically estimated sampling rate is subsequently used to parameterize the spectral analysis.

Digital Signal Processing

Prior to spectral evaluation, the digitized signal is weighted using a Hamming window to reduce edge effects in the frequency-domain analysis. Spectral analysis is then performed using the Goertzel algorithm, which is particularly well suited for the efficient computation of individual frequency components.

Targeted reference frequencies in the range of the mains frequency and its harmonics are evaluated. These include frequency bands centered around 50 Hz, 100 Hz, and 150 Hz, each with a defined tolerance. The required Goertzel coefficients are computed at runtime based on the measured sampling rate, allowing deviations in the sampling frequency to be compensated.

Feature Extraction and Classification

The magnitudes obtained from the spectral analysis are logarithmically scaled to improve numerical stability and subsequently used as input features for classification. Classification is performed using a compact fully connected neural network consisting of nine input neurons, one hidden layer with 20 neurons, and three output neurons representing the operating states.

The hyperbolic tangent function is employed as the activation function in the hidden layer, while a softmax function is used in the output layer. The weight matrices and bias vectors obtained during offline training are stored as constants within the firmware, ensuring that inference on the microcontroller exactly matches the previously validated model.

LoRa Data Transmission

After classification, selected system information is aggregated together with the classification result into a compact data packet. This packet includes, among other parameters, the system uptime, the module temperature, and a class identifier, resulting in a total payload size of only a few bytes.

Data transmission is performed via the connected LoRa radio module using serial AT commands. Prior to periodic data transmission, the device joins the LoRaWAN network, after which the

payload data are transmitted at regular intervals. By performing classification locally, the transmission of continuous raw measurement data is avoided, significantly reducing communication overhead and energy consumption.

The complete implementation of the described ESP32 firmware is documented in **Appendix A.1** for the sake of clarity and reproducibility.

3.4 Data Analysis and Training in Julia

To develop and validate the classification model, the measurement data recorded by the ESP32 were evaluated offline using the Julia programming language. The raw data consist of timestamps and corresponding ADC values and form the basis for the subsequent analysis and model development.

Data processing in Julia deliberately follows the implementation used on the embedded system. In particular, the same Goertzel algorithm as in the ESP32 firmware is employed to ensure consistent feature extraction. This identical signal processing guarantees that the features obtained during training correspond exactly to those later computed on the microcontroller. The complete implementation of the offline data analysis and training workflow is documented in **Appendix A.2**.

The Goertzel algorithm was selected because it is significantly more resource-efficient than a full discrete Fourier transform when only specific frequency components are of interest. For the analysis, spectral components in the range of the mains frequency and its first harmonics are specifically evaluated. The resulting amplitude values are subsequently logarithmically scaled and normalized to provide stable inputs for the classification model.

Due to the limited number of measurements available per operating state within the timeframe of the laboratory exercise, the existing spectral data were synthetically augmented. To this end, additive noise scaled proportionally to the signal amplitude was introduced to realistically model natural signal variability and expected ADC measurement noise. This data augmentation improves the generalization capability of the model and reduces the risk of overfitting.

A fully connected neural network with nine input neurons, one hidden layer containing 20 neurons, and three output neurons was trained as the classifier. Optimization was performed using gradient descent over multiple training iterations. The selected network architecture represents a suitable compromise between classification accuracy and computational complexity.

After completion of training, the resulting weight matrices and bias vectors were directly transferred to the ESP32 firmware. Consequently, inference on the microcontroller corresponds exactly to the model trained and validated in Julia. Tests conducted on non-augmented spectral data demonstrated reliable discrimination of the three considered operating states.

The computational load of the classification task remains low on the ESP32, as only basic matrix operations and elementary activation functions are executed. The activation function used in the

hidden layer is already available in the standard mathematical library, eliminating the need for additional numerical approximations.

The model parameters used in the firmware are provided in **Appendix A.3**.

3.5 LoRaWAN Communication and Integration into The Things Network

3.5.1 Purpose and Role of the Communication Layer

In the presented system, wireless communication is used exclusively for the transmission of highly condensed result data. Since signal processing and classification are performed entirely on the embedded system, no time-resolved raw measurement data need to be transmitted. Instead, the classification result is sent together with selected system information to a backend via a LoRaWAN connection.

The Things Network (TTN) is used as the network server. TTN handles the management of the LoRaWAN communication, the network join procedure of the end device, and the forwarding of received uplink messages to the application layer. No further processing of the measurement signals is performed in the backend.

3.5.2 Device and Application Integration in TTN

To enable communication via TTN, a dedicated application was created and the LoRa module used in the system was registered as an end device. Device identification is performed using the unique identifiers defined by the LoRaWAN standard (DevEUI, AppEUI, and AppKey). Communication was implemented using the Over-The-Air Activation (OTAA) mode, which enables a secure and dynamic network join procedure.

After successful registration, the end device appears in the TTN dashboard, where its status can be monitored. The dashboard provides information such as the LoRaWAN version in use, the selected frequency band, and the most recently received uplink messages.

Figure 3.2: TTN dashboard showing the registered end device and the most recently received uplink message

3.5.3 Network Join and Uplink Transmission

The network join procedure of the sensor node is performed using the OTAA mechanism. After a successful join, the end device is authorized to periodically transmit uplink messages to the LoRaWAN gateway. Communication between the microcontroller and the LoRa module is implemented via a serial UART interface, with the radio module being controlled using AT commands.

Following the successful network join, data packets are transmitted at regular intervals. These transmissions initially serve as a functional verification of the communication chain and ensure that both the wireless link and the backend connection operate correctly.

3.5.4 Structure of the Transmitted Payload

The payload transmitted via LoRaWAN consists of a compact byte array containing multiple information fields. Among the transmitted data are the system uptime, internal status information, and a class identifier representing the result of the local classification process. This compact representation keeps the payload size small and well suited for LoRaWAN transmission.

Since LoRaWAN transports raw byte arrays only, interpretation of the payload is required on the backend side. For this purpose, a payload formatter is configured within TTN, which converts the received byte stream into structured and human-readable data.

```
{
  "temperature": 27.2,
  "uptime": 206
}
```

Figure 3.3: Structured payload after decoding in the TTN backend

3.5.5 Payload Decoding in the TTN Backend

Payload decoding is performed using a JavaScript-based payload formatter that is directly configured within TTN. The formatter first validates the length of the received byte array and then decodes the individual data fields according to their predefined encoding schemes. These include, among others, integer and floating-point values with a defined byte order.

The decoded data are automatically displayed by TTN as a structured JSON object and are therefore available for further processing or visualization. The complete implementation of the payload formatter used in TTN is documented in **Appendix A.4**.

```
function decodeUplink(input) {
  var bytes = input.bytes;

  if (bytes.length < 8) {
    return {
      data: {},
      warnings: ["Payload too short"],
      errors: []
    };
  }

  // Decode uptime (4 bytes, big-endian)
  var uptime = (bytes[0] << 24) | (bytes[1] << 16) | (bytes[2] << 8) | bytes[3];

  // Decode float (4 bytes, little-endian IEEE 754)
  var tempBytes = new Uint8Array([bytes[4], bytes[5], bytes[6], bytes[7]]);
  var tempView = new DataView(tempBytes.buffer);
  var temperature = Number(tempView.getFloat32(0, true).toFixed(1));

  return {
    data: {
      uptime: uptime,
      temperature: temperature
    },
    warnings: [],
    errors: []
  };
}
```

Figure 3.4: JavaScript-based payload formatter in the TTN backend

3.5.6 Monitoring of Ongoing LoRaWAN Communication

During operation, received uplink messages can be observed using the live monitor of The Things Network (TTN). For each received packet, metadata such as timestamps, gateway information, and radio-related parameters are displayed. These data are used for technical verification of the communication link and confirm stable data exchange between the sensor node and the backend.

Uplink	Temperatur	Uptime	RSSI [dBm]	SNR [dB]	SF	Gateway
1	27.2 °C	206 s	-113	-3.25	SF11	iot-labor-hrw
2	27.1 °C	534 s	-114	+2.0	SF9	eui-a8044...

Table 3.1: Comparison of uplink measurement values for different spreading factors (SF9, SF11)

Interpretation:

SF11 provides a longer communication range and increased airtime, remaining stable even at lower signal-to-noise ratios. In contrast, SF9 results in shorter airtime and reduced range but offers higher energy efficiency. This clearly illustrates the typical LoRaWAN trade-off between communication range and energy consumption.

4. Results and Evaluation

4.1 Observation of the Current Signals

The functionality of the developed system was evaluated using recorded current signals. The following figures illustrate the temporal behavior of the sensor signal for different operating states of the electrical load.

Figure 4.1 shows the complete time-domain waveform of the sensor signal in the *cold* operating state. The signal exhibits a pronounced periodic structure, with a fundamental frequency corresponding to the mains frequency. Despite the comparatively low current amplitude, the dynamic range of the analog-to-digital converter is effectively utilized by means of the applied offset and amplification stage.

For a more detailed analysis of the signal shape, Figure 4.2 presents a magnified section of the first 150 ms of the same measurement. This representation reveals that the current waveform is not ideally sinusoidal. In addition, high-frequency components and superimposed noise are present. These characteristics indicate a non-linear power control of the hot air blower, for example due to phase-angle control or thyristor-based regulation.

The presented time-domain signals demonstrate that the sensor system provides stable and analyzable measurements even at low current levels. A direct conversion of the ADC values into physical current quantities was deliberately omitted for the embedded processing, as the classification relies exclusively on relative spectral features, thereby avoiding additional computational overhead.

Figure 4.1: Time-domain signal of the cold operating state

Figure 4.2: Time-domain signal (first 150 ms) of the cold operating state

4.2 Frequency Analysis of the Current Signals

For further analysis of the recorded current signals, a frequency-domain analysis was performed. The objective was to identify characteristic spectral differences between the investigated operating states and to use these differences as a basis for subsequent classification.

Figure 4.3 shows the magnitude spectrum of the current signal in the *cold* operating state, computed using a discrete Fourier transform. A dominant peak at the mains frequency of 50 Hz is clearly visible, along with additional peaks at integer multiples of this frequency. These harmonics arise from the non-linear power control of the electrical load and are typical for electronically regulated household appliances.

In comparison, Figure 4.4 illustrates the frequency spectrum of the *max* operating state. In this case, significantly higher amplitudes are observed both at the fundamental frequency and at selected harmonic components. At the same time, the relative contribution of higher-order harmonics is less pronounced, indicating a more uniform current waveform during full-load operation. In this operating mode, the internal power regulation interferes less with the current flow, resulting in a waveform that more closely resembles an ideal sinusoid.

For the later implementation on the microcontroller, a full FFT computation was deliberately omitted. Instead, the Goertzel algorithm was employed to selectively compute individual frequency components. The corresponding Goertzel spectra are shown in Figure 4.5 for the *cold* state and in Figure 4.6 for the *max* state.

The Goertzel-based analysis reduces the spectral information to a small set of selected reference frequencies. Clear differences in spectral energy between the operating states can be observed, particularly at the mains frequency and its harmonics. These differences are reproducible and therefore well suited as robust features for state classification.

By focusing on a limited number of relevant frequency components, the computational effort is significantly reduced without losing essential information. The resulting spectral values serve as input features for the embedded neural network and form the link between signal processing and classification.

Figure 4.3: FFT magnitude spectrum of the cold operating state

Figure 4.4: FFT magnitude spectrum of the maximum operating state

Figure 4.5: Goertzel spectrum of the cold state

Figure 4.6: Goertzel spectrum of the maximum state

4.3 Classification Results and Uplink Output

Based on the frequency-domain features described in Section 4.2, state classification was performed entirely on the embedded system. The input features of the neural network consist of the spectral energy values of selected reference frequencies computed using the Goertzel algorithm. These features were normalized prior to classification and subsequently fed into the neural network implemented on the microcontroller.

Classification is executed cyclically after completion of each measurement and analysis window. For every measurement cycle, exactly one class decision is generated, representing the current operating state of the electrical load. In the investigated scenario, the three defined states *cold*, *rest*, and *max* could be reliably distinguished. No abrupt or inconsistent class assignments were observed during the experiments, indicating sufficient separability of the selected features.

The classification result is not transmitted as a continuous signal but in a highly condensed form. In addition to the class identifier, only selected system information such as the system uptime and the module temperature is included in the transmitted data packet. As a result, the transmitted payload size remains very small, which is particularly advantageous for energy-efficient LoRaWAN applications.

Transmission of the classification results is performed via the LoRaWAN module to the TTN backend. There, the received uplink packets are interpreted using a payload decoder and displayed in a structured format. Figure 4.7 shows exemplary successfully received uplink messages, in which the transmitted class information consistently corresponds to the current operating state.

The agreement between the locally computed class decision and the class identifier displayed in the backend confirms the correct operation of the complete processing chain. In particular, the results demonstrate that embedded classification operates reliably without dependence on cloud-based processing, with the backend serving solely for visualization and further handling of the transmitted results.

Overall, these results confirm that the combination of local signal processing, embedded classification, and wireless transmission of condensed results has been implemented in a practical and reliable manner.

eui-70b3d57ed0073d6b	Dec 3, 2025 10:34:45	8	28	2	{ class_id: 0, class_name: "REST", temperature_c: 28, uptime_seconds: 164 }
eui-70b3d57ed0073d6b	Dec 3, 2025 10:35:02	8	29	1	{ class_id: 0, class_name: "REST", temperature_c: 28, uptime_seconds: 122 }
eui-70b3d57ed0073d6b	Dec 3, 2025 10:35:20	8	30	1	{ class_id: 1, class_name: "COLD", temperature_c: 28, uptime_seconds: 139 }
eui-70b3d57ed0073d6b	Dec 3, 2025 10:35:37	8	31	2	{ class_id: 1, class_name: "COLD", temperature_c: 28, uptime_seconds: 157 }
eui-70b3d57ed0073d6b	Dec 3, 2025 10:35:55	8	32	2	{ class_id: 1, class_name: "COLD", temperature_c: 28, uptime_seconds: 174 }
eui-70b3d57ed0073d6b	Dec 3, 2025 10:36:12	8	33	2	{ class_id: 1, class_name: "COLD", temperature_c: 28, uptime_seconds: 192 }
eui-70b3d57ed0073d6b	Dec 3, 2025 10:36:29	8	34	1	{ class_id: 2, class_name: "MAX", temperature_c: 28, uptime_seconds: 209 }

Figure 4.7: Examples of TTN uplink messages with encoded uptime, temperature, and class ID

4.4 Discussion of the Results

The conducted measurements and analyses demonstrate that the developed sensor system is capable of reliably capturing and distinguishing the intended operating states of the electrical load. The time-domain current signals already reveal clear differences between the examined states, particularly in terms of amplitude, waveform shape, and periodicity. These differences form the basis for the subsequent spectral analysis.

The frequency-domain analysis using the FFT confirms the expected behavior of mains-powered electrical loads. In all active operating states, pronounced spectral components occur at the mains frequency of 50 Hz and its harmonics. In the maximum operating state, significantly higher spectral energy levels are observed, whereas in reduced operating modes additional harmonic components are present. These changes can be attributed to the internal power control of the hot air blower, which actively modulates the current waveform.

The Goertzel-based analysis proves to be particularly well suited for the employed embedded system. By restricting the evaluation to a small number of carefully selected frequency components, the relevant spectral information is strongly condensed without losing essential classification features. At the same time, the computational effort remains low, enabling efficient execution on a resource-constrained microcontroller. The Goertzel results show consistent and reproducible differences between the operating states and confirm the suitability of the selected reference frequencies.

The subsequent classification using the embedded neural network effectively exploits these feature differences. The stable class assignments observed throughout the measurement series indicate that the model is neither overly sensitive to noise nor overfitted. A key advantage is that the classification is performed entirely locally and therefore operates independently of the wireless communication link. The cloud connection serves solely for transmission and visualization of the results.

The LoRaWAN communication also exhibited stable behavior during the experiments. The observed RSSI and SNR values were within the expected range for an indoor environment. Differences between various spreading factors reflect the typical trade-off between communication range and energy efficiency but did not negatively affect the correct transmission of the classification results.

In summary, the measurement results confirm the proper operation of the complete measurement and classification chain. The combination of analog signal conditioning, local frequency analysis, embedded classification, and energy-efficient wireless transmission represents a robust approach for intelligent sensor systems. The results further demonstrate that reliable state classification can be achieved even with limited computational resources, provided that feature extraction is performed in a targeted and system-oriented manner.

4.5 Fulfillment of the Requirements

The requirements defined for the sensor system within the scope of the laboratory project were fully implemented in the present work. The following section summarizes the extent to which the individual objectives were achieved.

A central requirement was the reliable acquisition of the current signal of an electrical load. By using a galvanically isolated current sensor in combination with an appropriate offset and amplification stage, a stable and analyzable sensor signal was obtained. The measurements show that the available dynamic range of the analog-to-digital converter is effectively utilized and that reproducible results are achieved even at low current levels.

All digital signal processing steps were required to be executed on the embedded system. This requirement was fulfilled through the implementation of time-discrete sampling, spectral analysis using the Goertzel algorithm, and subsequent classification. The selection of a limited number of targeted frequency components enabled computationally efficient processing and proved sufficient to distinguish between the considered operating states.

Another key objective was local classification using an embedded neural network. The measurement results demonstrate that class assignments are stable and consistent. By transferring the trained model parameters from the offline analysis to the firmware, consistency between training behavior and runtime behavior is ensured. As a result, the required embedded machine learning functionality was successfully realized.

Wireless transmission of the results via LoRaWAN also meets the specified requirements. By limiting the payload to condensed result data, the transmitted data volume remains small, enabling energy-efficient communication. The successful visualization of the received uplink messages in the TTN backend confirms the correct integration of the sensor node into the network infrastructure.

Overall, it can be concluded that all essential functional and system-level requirements of the laboratory project were fulfilled. The developed sensor system represents a complete processing chain from current measurement to wireless transmission of classification results and therefore successfully meets the objectives of the *Sensorsystems* module.

A Anhang

A.1 Finaler ESP Code

```
1 // Combined ESP32 sketch: Goertzel -> NN inference -> LoRa transmit
2 // ----- includes -----
3 #include <math.h>
4
5 // ----- LoRa UART pins (unchanged) -----
6 #define RXD2 16
7 #define TXD2 17
8 #define SerialLora Serial2
9
10 // ----- LoRa / status variables -----
11 String resp_time, resp_temp;
12 unsigned long startSeconds = 0;
13 unsigned long uptime = 0;
14 float temp = 0.0;
15
16 // ----- Goertzel configuration -----
17 #define sense_pin 4
18 #define V_offset 1.23 // determined with 0 reading
19 #define amplification 3.8 // measured with oszi
20
21 const int buffer_len = 2000;
22 const int N_freq = 9;
23 const float f_ref[N_freq] = { 49.5, 50.0, 50.5, 99.5, 100.0, 100.5, 149.5, 150.0, 150.5 };
24
25 float fs = 0.0;
26 int x_raw[buffer_len];
27 unsigned long t_raw[buffer_len];
28 float current_samples[buffer_len];
29 float t_s[buffer_len];
30 float coeff[N_freq];
31 float window_buf[buffer_len];
32 float mag[N_freq];
33
34 // ----- NN architecture -----
35 const int nInput = N_freq;
36 const int nHidden = 20;
37 const int nOutput = 3; // rest/cold/max
38
39
40 float Wl[nHidden][nInput] = {
41   {-0.05223106157992093, -0.038863221991343365, -0.024912165442704855, 0.17993726703240018,
42     0.18566661942272705, 0.175025325765853, 0.17807737580998917, 0.15054470443332477,
43     0.18261701457013307},
44   {0.03629173357293167, -0.04574114121755122, -0.029872122275227214, -0.24907599374081169,
45     -0.25887855324942183, -0.1906270531816594, 0.44578532935059556, 0.45049321820595045,
46     0.43354472168779945},
47   {-0.058946843823207626, -0.020234215001328687, -0.03634598427576315, 0.17578675737437635,
48     0.18486387782379365, 0.1644929788241676, 0.1634493801966925, 0.18854597720762317,
49     0.17073762167266962},
50   {0.0257551407368492, 0.027099608571037905, 0.04046160646324992, -0.166376832463197,
51     -0.15586594210363489, -0.15529660422178193, -0.1449605620652045, -0.13712478506605194,
52     -0.14623431375128237},
53   {0.030328043793417338, 0.025234974020960244, 0.03424230289043022, -0.1451225514400921,
54     -0.12523811545881186, -0.13268347918629786, -0.1607866429045878, -0.1589681315906946,
55     -0.15782468248099757},
56   {0.029140993056605714, 0.039007734967134916, 0.04601919521462245, -0.13270520809013844,
57     -0.11384238726911054, -0.12351628169237043, -0.17425019207368075, -0.1733362528490477,
58     -0.18767821600996842},
59   {-0.10662697789384262, -0.04161104306711665, -0.0421790965813678, 0.23572734916361504,
60     0.24824664619113473, 0.19794463779980564, -0.21619777361904366, -0.2255209713697197,
61     -0.22051824947569107},
62   {0.025043363749996564, 0.05374165199360599, 0.03185987039965992, -0.1459894384185183,
63     -0.15322795801893227, -0.14645560236372254, -0.175522543656269, -0.1719620750379858,
64     -0.16874413111034048},
65   {-0.2135890813189327, -0.12182182948232968, -0.1104727106827796, 0.4708095562885923,
66     0.4657283250550695, 0.3812448784181379, -0.36895509537250254, -0.3287305804976945,
67     -0.35869107192034244},
68   {-0.034576330836168276, -0.02965282895813582, -0.019690065737339404, 0.14378096894026304,
69     0.1572512014314825, 0.14312195687793597, 0.1356408461518148, 0.14810919352675236,
70     0.14239536522293755},
71   {-0.024937501030930172, -0.08186158099276317, -0.07064278964993498, -0.08215677107170817,
72     -0.08327660179925814, -0.060321240082087405, 0.2969330785575319, 0.3117293368105399,
73     0.33413667590704},
74   {-0.17553817646926978, -0.10701304492353089, -0.10539194242922721, 0.2392971965392584,
75     0.2295789870303206, 0.2247848906622307, -0.007076914510581352, 0.008823216490049262,
```

```

0.016373367743401132},
53 {-0.028360489719664452, -0.04525010703900485, -0.05747022096637156, 0.17134231525184454,
0.1853686762442399, 0.1831307090723432, 0.18724155439964024, 0.20789484872976602,
0.18073480805490424},
54 {-0.027404017387014104, -0.024309212025402385, -0.054043620668051365, 0.10407765902750324,
0.10342447111412237, 0.09567327107110603, 0.16714049496580202, 0.15993472405335263,
0.17813385183747946},
55 {0.011526965911454466, 0.045908034003154116, 0.04983269864207979, 0.1034381245688707,
0.10888689574639032, 0.06176928007037954, -0.2645697675384189, -0.2824880749702104,
-0.27170415508372414},
56 {-0.191107798027361, -0.13211386882424278, -0.15208192991176867, 0.33732669937430276,
0.32794175958698235, 0.2994272101122255, -0.11018553431073197, -0.12329462220449748,
-0.08937838752431403},
57 {-0.11446588237125767, -0.015029993061682236, -0.03827833639492076, 0.35012448112413713,
0.3305817287740821, 0.2792254378531181, -0.4111935893477785, -0.3981508198423714,
-0.39336823612988164},
58 {-0.051200105183687755, -0.06420867215005298, -0.04697893393583206, 0.19983747748055078,
0.21542543306446876, 0.20087190371744, 0.11607596405958676, 0.11412723730374336,
0.12134190280620226},
59 {-0.0844296693843661, -0.023791536102608906, -0.046718749197634586, 0.12085434892599023,
0.13235228970480264, 0.12341599312249978, -0.08186400577741734, -0.06872176383083331,
-0.0531196068804277},
60 {-0.18190977022134244, -0.06832860809928182, -0.09034874964606046, 0.38111965793944885,
0.3659622669794402, 0.31423027184505975, -0.3012665701370323, -0.2989230984970276,
-0.30370579217634197}
61 };
62
63
64 float b1[nHidden] = {
65 -0.0786646812805507,
66 -0.11120266989841315,
67 -0.08003066040562236,
68 0.0635594781691335,
69 0.07112522729343,
70 0.07320796182152323,
71 0.02092752355311026,
72 0.06887153400280827,
73 0.00997366424291799,
74 -0.06324364675409677,
75 -0.1024555500584641,
76 -0.06657201482645803,
77 -0.08699247073960406,
78 -0.06727149616688284,
79 0.08371129408529032,
80 -0.06084008045615208,
81 0.06903132065487895,
82 -0.06938633028463377,
83 -0.012070210506336387,
84 0.01644402990533841
85 };
86
87 float W2[3][20] = {
88 {
89 -0.5068181924454883, -0.26573354336288557, -0.5033685524731665,
90 0.3828920166690258, 0.39747049362785153, 0.41991165452612156,
91 -0.035400430139482665, 0.43917977628475663, -0.15562013806214564,
92 -0.3745780024613727, -0.3838524297202577, -0.42237767597768167,
93 -0.5582237846204359, -0.36034424148043587, 0.2525815906016523,
94 -0.39332540891803824, 0.05862152761547939, -0.4711974019862762,
95 -0.09172199154105151, -0.10613253639531851
96 },
97 {
98 0.2545342473294832, -0.5926077732881144, 0.24774022920810532,
99 -0.2212380832818837, -0.16100055754890366, -0.15209470430846114,
100 0.4531987057159532, -0.19481711999878493, 1.0119113282570955,
101 0.18866896463819233, -0.18077230216992876, 0.42508864196202806,
102 0.2664942683448314, 0.11514153021279432, 0.21270253184142654,
103 0.6265156334509494, 0.7801604872332625, 0.3061231333412953,
104 0.22277231660759556, 0.7583907215647149
105 },
106 {
107 0.2400701632306189, 0.840244016936342, 0.25165757741842304,
108 -0.21149693979700884, -0.2258196456038587, -0.2677672903204078,
109 -0.4192191197679213, -0.25283012354780143, -0.8561199587702859,
110 0.19764548994479086, 0.5396852222583951, -0.00001807300111219597,
111 0.2975389500027614, 0.2547118061414534, -0.46268576042374554,
112 -0.2242938268780296, -0.8143473398999347, 0.16002230416940735,
113 -0.1270286205740329, -0.6598111446022946
114 }
115 };
116 float b2[3] = {
117 0.2870044351663108,

```

```

118     -0.05757139778958312,
119     -0.22943303737672954
120 };
121
122 // ===== End weights and biases =====
123
124 // small temporary arrays for inference
125 float z1[nHidden], a1[nHidden];
126 float z2[nOutput], a2[nOutput];
127
128 // some constants
129 const float eps_log = 1e-12f; // avoid log10(0)
130 const int SAMPLES_TO_COLLECT = buffer.len;
131
132 // packet buffer (we will pack uptime(4) + temp(4) + class(1) = 9 bytes)
133 byte lora_packet[9];
134 int last_pred = 0;
135
136 // ----- function prototypes -----
137 void waitforTransmit(String payloadHex);
138 void waitForJoin();
139 float readTemp();
140 unsigned long readRTC();
141 unsigned long rtcToSeconds(String rtcString);
142
143 void collectSamples();
144 void goertzel_init();
145 void goertzel_compute();
146 void findMaxVal();
147 void findRMS();
148
149 void nn_predict(float input[], float output_probs[]);
150 int argmax(float arr[], int len);
151 void sendPredictionOverLoRa(int class_id);
152
153 // ----- setup -----
154 void setup() {
155     Serial.begin(500000);
156     Serial.println("");
157     SerialLora.begin(9600, SERIAL_8N1, RXD2, TXD2);
158     delay(1000);
159
160     // Initialize RTC (will set startSeconds)
161     waitForJoin();
162     startSeconds = readRTC();
163
164     collectSamples();
165     goertzel_init();
166 }
167
168 // ----- loop -----
169 void loop() {
170     collectSamples();
171
172     goertzel_compute();
173
174     float x_input[nInput];
175     for (int i = 0; i < nInput; i++) {
176         float v = mag[i];
177         if (!(isfinite(v)) || v < 0.0f) v = 0.0f; // guard
178         x_input[i] = log10f(v + eps_log);
179     }
180
181     // predict with NN
182     float probs[nOutput];
183     nn_predict(x_input, probs);
184     int pred = argmax(probs, nOutput); // 0..2
185     Serial.println(pred);
186     // send the result via LoRa (uptime + temp + class)
187     temp = readTemp(); // update temp
188     unsigned long nowSeconds = readRTC();
189     uptime = nowSeconds - startSeconds;
190
191     // Pack uptime (4 bytes big-endian)
192     lora_packet[0] = (uptime >> 24) & 0xFF;
193     lora_packet[1] = (uptime >> 16) & 0xFF;
194     lora_packet[2] = (uptime >> 8) & 0xFF;
195     lora_packet[3] = uptime & 0xFF;
196
197     // Pack float temp
198     union {
199         float f;

```

```

200     byte b[4];
201 } tempUnion;
202 tempUnion.f = temp;
203 for (int i = 0; i < 4; i++) {
204     lora_packet[4 + i] = tempUnion.b[i];
205 }
206
207 // Append predicted class
208 lora_packet[8] = (byte)pred;
209
210 // Convert packet to hex string
211 String hexStr = "";
212 for (int i = 0; i < 9; i++) {
213     if (lora_packet[i] < 16) hexStr += "0";
214     hexStr += String(lora_packet[i], HEX);
215 }
216 Serial.println(hexStr);
217 waitforTransmit(hexStr);
218
219 delay(10000);
220 // wait for next reading
221 //delay(10000);
222 }
223
224 // ----- LoRa helper functions -----
225 void waitforTransmit(String payload) {
226     Serial.print("Sending HEX packet: ");
227     Serial.println(payload);
228
229     SerialLora.print("AT+MSGHEX=" + payload + "\r\n");
230     String resp;
231     bool joined = false;
232     unsigned long joinStart = millis();
233
234     while (!joined && millis() - joinStart < 30000) { // wait max 30s
235         if (SerialLora.available()) {
236             resp = SerialLora.readStringUntil('\n');
237             resp.trim();
238             Serial.print("LoRa response: ");
239             Serial.println(resp);
240             if (resp.indexOf("Done") >= 0 || resp.indexOf("already") >= 0) {
241                 joined = true;
242             }
243         }
244     }
245
246     if (!joined) {
247         Serial.println("MSG timed out!");
248     } else {
249         Serial.println("MSG sent");
250     }
251 }
252
253 void waitforJoin() {
254     Serial.println("Joining Network...");
255     SerialLora.print("AT+JOIN\r\n");
256
257     String resp;
258     bool joined = false;
259     unsigned long joinStart = millis();
260
261     while (!joined && millis() - joinStart < 30000) { // wait max 30s
262         if (SerialLora.available()) {
263             resp = SerialLora.readStringUntil('\n');
264             resp.trim();
265             Serial.print("LoRa response: ");
266             Serial.println(resp);
267             if (resp.indexOf("Done") >= 0 || resp.indexOf("already") >= 0) {
268                 joined = true;
269             }
270         }
271     }
272
273     if (!joined) {
274         Serial.println("Join timed out!");
275     } else {
276         Serial.println("Joined Network");
277     }
278 }
279
280 float readTemp() {
281     SerialLora.print("AT+TEMP\r\n");

```

```

363     for (int i = 0; i < buffer-len; i++) {
364         float w1 = 2.0f * M_PI * ((float)i) / ((float)buffer-len - 1.0f);
365         window.buf[i] = 0.54f - 0.46f * cosf(w1);
366     }
367 }
368
369 void goertzel_compute() {
370     // reset
371     for (int i = 0; i < N-freq; i++) {
372         mag[i] = 0.0f;
373     }
374     float tmp = 0.0f;
375     float data = 0.0f;
376     float s1[N-freq];
377     float s2[N-freq];
378     for (int i = 0; i < N-freq; i++) { s1[i] = 0.0f; s2[i] = 0.0f; }
379
380     for (int n = 0; n < buffer-len; n++) {
381         data = current_samples[n] * window.buf[n]; // window
382         for (int i = 0; i < N-freq; i++) {
383             tmp = (coeff[i] * s1[i]) - s2[i] + data;
384             s2[i] = s1[i];
385             s1[i] = tmp;
386         }
387     }
388     for (int i = 0; i < N-freq; i++) {
389         mag[i] = (s1[i] * s1[i]) + (s2[i] * s2[i]) - (s1[i] * s2[i] * coeff[i]);
390         if (!isfinite(mag[i]) || mag[i] < 0.0f) mag[i] = 0.0f;
391         Serial.print(f-ref[i]); Serial.print(" "); Serial.println(mag[i]);
392     }
393 }
394
395 // ----- NN inference -----
396 void nn_predict(float input[], float output-probs[]) {
397     // input: length nInput
398     // compute Z1 = W1 * input + b1
399     for (int i = 0; i < nHidden; i++) {
400         float s = 0.0f;
401         for (int j = 0; j < nInput; j++) {
402             s += W1[i][j] * input[j];
403         }
404         s += b1[i];
405         z1[i] = s;
406         a1[i] = tanhf(z1[i]);
407     }
408
409     // Z2 = W2 * A1 + b2
410     for (int i = 0; i < nOutput; i++) {
411         float s = 0.0f;
412         for (int j = 0; j < nHidden; j++) {
413             s += W2[i][j] * a1[j];
414         }
415         s += b2[i];
416         z2[i] = s;
417     }
418
419     // softmax
420     float maxx = z2[0];
421     for (int i = 1; i < nOutput; i++) if (z2[i] > maxx) maxx = z2[i];
422
423     float sumexp = 0.0f;
424     for (int i = 0; i < nOutput; i++) {
425         output-probs[i] = expf(z2[i] - maxx);
426         sumexp += output-probs[i];
427     }
428     for (int i = 0; i < nOutput; i++) output-probs[i] /= sumexp;
429 }
430
431 int argmax(float arr[], int len) {
432     int idx = 0;
433     float best = arr[0];
434     for (int i = 1; i < len; i++) {
435         if (arr[i] > best) {
436             best = arr[i];
437             idx = i;
438         }
439     }
440     return idx;
441 }

```

```

282 unsigned long start = millis();
283 while (!SerialLora.available() && millis() - start < 2000) delay(10);
284
285 if (!SerialLora.available()) {
286     Serial.println("TEMP timeout");
287     return 0.0f;
288 }
289
290 String resp = SerialLora.readStringUntil('\n');
291 resp.trim();
292 Serial.print("RAW Temp: ");
293 Serial.println(resp);
294
295 // Expected "+TEMP: xx.x"
296 int idx = resp.indexOf(":");
297 if (idx >= 0) {
298     String num = resp.substring(idx + 1);
299     num.trim();
300     return num.toFloat();
301 }
302 return 0.0f;
303 }
304
305 unsigned long readRTC() {
306     SerialLora.print("AT+RTC\r\n");
307     unsigned long start = millis();
308     while (!SerialLora.available() && millis() - start < 2000) delay(10);
309
310     if (!SerialLora.available()) {
311         Serial.println("RTC timeout");
312         return 0UL;
313     }
314
315     String resp = SerialLora.readStringUntil('\n');
316     resp.trim();
317     Serial.print("RAW RTC: ");
318     Serial.println(resp);
319
320     return rtcToSeconds(resp);
321 }
322
323 // Example: "+RTC: YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss"
324 unsigned long rtcToSeconds(String rtcString) {
325     if (rtcString.length() < 25) return 0UL;
326     int hour = rtcString.substring(17, 19).toInt();
327     int min = rtcString.substring(20, 22).toInt();
328     int sec = rtcString.substring(23, 25).toInt();
329
330     return (unsigned long)hour * 3600UL + (unsigned long)min * 60UL + (unsigned long)sec;
331 }
332
333 // ----- Goertzel and sampling functions -----
334 void collectSamples() {
335     // Collect buffer.len samples with 100 us spacing
336     for (int i = 0; i < buffer.len; i++) {
337         t.raw[i] = micros();
338         x.raw[i] = analogRead(sense-pin);
339         delayMicroseconds(100);
340     }
341     // convert to time and current
342     for (int i = 0; i < buffer.len; i++) {
343         t.s[i] = ((float)t.raw[i] - (float)t.raw[0]) * 0.000001f;
344         current.samples[i] = ((float)x.raw[i] * 0.000805f - V.offset) * (5.0f/(2.0f*amplification)); //
345         // convert to amps
346     }
347     // estimate fs
348     fs = 10.0f / (t.s[30] - t.s[20]); // approximate sampling rate
349     Serial.print("f.s= ");
350     Serial.print(fs);
351     Serial.println(" Hz");
352 }
353
354 void goertzel-init() {
355     int k = 0;
356     float w = 0.0f;
357     // compute coeff
358     for (int i = 0; i < N.freq; i++) {
359         k = (int)round(((float)buffer.len * f.ref[i]) / fs);
360         w = 2.0f * M.PI * ((float)k) / ((float)buffer.len);
361         coeff[i] = 2.0f * cosf(w);
362     }
363     // hamming window

```

A.2 Analyze Data JL

```
1
2 using DelimitedFiles
3 using FFTW
4 using Plots
5 using Statistics
6 using DelimitedFiles
7 using LaTeXStrings
8 cd(@--DIR--)
9 gr()
10
11 plot-font = "Computer Modern"
12 default(fontfamily=plot-font,
13         linewidth=2, framestyle=:box, label=nothing, grid=false)
14
15 function goertzel-init()
16     k = 0.0;
17     w = 0.0;
18     for i = 1:N-freq
19         k = round(convert(Float64,N) * convert(Float64,freq-ref[i]) / convert(Float64,fs));
20         println(k);
21         w = 2.0 * pi * convert(Float64,k) / convert(Float64,N);
22         coeff[i] = 2.0 * cos(w);
23     end
24     #Hamming-Fenster
25     for i = 1:N
26         w = 2.0 * pi * convert(Float64,i) / convert(Float64,N);
27         window[i] = 0.54 - 0.46 * cos(w);
28     end
29 end
30
31 #Goertzel Algorithmus, Berechnen des Leistungs-Spektrums
32 function goertzel(adcData)
33     tmp = 0.0;
34     data = 0.0;
35     mag = zeros(N-freq);
36     s1 = zeros(N-freq);
37     s2 = zeros(N-freq);
38     for n = 1:N
39         data = (convert(Float64,adcData[n]) - 2048.0) / 4095.0; #Umrechnung der ADC-Werte
40         data = data * window[n]; #Fensterung mit Hamming-Fenster
41         for i = 1:N-freq
42             tmp = (coeff[i] * s1[i]) - s2[i] + data;
43             s2[i] = s1[i];
44             s1[i] = tmp;
45         end
46     end
47     for i = 1:N-freq
48         mag[i] = (s1[i] * s1[i]) + (s2[i] * s2[i]) - (s1[i] * s2[i] * coeff[i]);
49     end
50     return mag
51 end
52
53
54 # === CONFIGURATION ===
55 filename = "Daten/heatgun-max.txt"
56 time-col = 1 # column index for time (microseconds)
57 value-col = 2 # column index for signal value
58 save-figs = true # set to true if you want to save plots as PNGs
59
60 # === LOAD DATA ===
61 data = readdlm(filename, ',', Int)
62
63
64
65 t-us = data[:, 1]
66 t-us = t-us .- t-us[1]
67 y = data[:, 2]
68 I = (y.-1525).*(3.3./4096).*(2.5./3.8).*1000;
69
70 t = t-us .* 1e-6 * 1000
71
72 # === PLOT SIGNAL ===
73 plot(t[1:500], I[1:500],
74      xlabel="Time in ms",
75      ylabel="Current in mA",
76      grid=true,
77      xtickfontsize=16,
78      ytickfontsize=16,
79      xguidefontsize=16,
```

```

80     yguidefontsize=16,
81     lw=1.5,
82     legend=false)
83
84 if save-figs
85     savefig("signal-time-zoom.png")
86 end
87
88 plot(t, I,
89     xlabel="Time in ms",
90     ylabel="Current in mA",
91     grid=true,
92     lw=1.5,
93     xtickfontsize=16,
94     ytickfontsize=16,
95     xguidefontsize=16,
96     yguidefontsize=16,
97     legend=false)
98
99 if save-figs
100     savefig("signal-time.png")
101 end
102 t = t ./ 1000
103 # === FFT ===
104 N = length(I)
105 dt = mean(diff(t))           # average time step (s)
106 fs = 1 / dt                 # sampling frequency (Hz)
107
108 Y = fft(I)
109 freqs = fftshift(fftshift(N, fs)) # center zero frequency
110 Yshift = fftshift(abs.(Y)./N)    # magnitude spectrum (normalized)
111
112 # === PLOT FFT ===
113 plot(freqs, Yshift,
114     xlabel="Frequency in Hz",
115     ylabel="Amplitude in mA",
116     lw=1.5,
117     grid=true,
118     xtickfontsize=16,
119     ytickfontsize=16,
120     xguidefontsize=16,
121     yguidefontsize=16,
122     legend=false,
123     xlims=(0.1,200))
124
125 if save-figs
126     savefig("fft-spectrum.png")
127 end
128
129 max-freq = 200
130 freq-ref = [49.5; 50; 50.5; 99.5; 100; 100.5; 149.5; 150; 150.5]
131 N-freq = length(freq-ref)
132 coeff = zeros(N-freq)
133 window = zeros(N)
134
135 goertzel_init()
136 output = goertzel(I)
137 goertzel_table = [freq-ref output] # combine into 2-column matrix
138 writedlm("goertzel-output.csv", goertzel_table, ',')
139
140 scatter(freq-ref, output, xlabel="Frequency (Hz)",
141     ylabel="Amplitude in mA",
142     grid=true,
143     xtickfontsize=16,
144     ytickfontsize=16,
145     xguidefontsize=16,
146     yguidefontsize=16,
147     xlims=(0.1,200),
148     ylims=(0,8e5))
149 if save-figs
150     savefig("gortzel.spectrum.png")
151 end

```

```

80     end
81 end
82
83 # plot loss
84 P = plot(loss-history, xlabel="Epoch", ylabel="Loss", title="Training Loss", legend=false)
85 display(P)
86 return W1, b1, W2, b2
87 end
88
89
90 #####
91 # TEST FUNCTION #
92 #####
93
94 function predict(W1,b1,W2,b2, x)
95     Z1 = W1 * x .+ b1
96     A1 = tanh.(Z1)
97     Z2 = W2 * A1 .+ b2
98     expZ = exp.(Z2 .- maximum(Z2))
99     A2 = expZ ./ sum(expZ)
100 return A2
101 end
102
103
104 #####
105 # LOAD DATA #
106 #####
107
108 df0 = CSV.read("Results/goertzel-output-rest.csv", DataFrame)
109 df1 = CSV.read("Results/goertzel-output-cold.csv", DataFrame)
110 df2 = CSV.read("Results/goertzel-output-max.csv", DataFrame)
111
112 amp0 = collect(df0.amplitude)
113 amp1 = collect(df1.amplitude)
114 amp2 = collect(df2.amplitude)
115
116 samples = 500
117
118 #####
119 # GENERATE 100 AUGMENTED SAMPLES #
120 #####
121
122 aug0 = augment.sample((amp0), samples)
123 aug1 = augment.sample((amp1), samples)
124 aug2 = augment.sample((amp2), samples)
125
126 # Normalize each sample
127 amp0_norm = log10.(aug0)
128 amp1_norm = log10.(aug1)
129 amp2_norm = log10.(aug2)
130
131 X_aug = [amp0_norm amp1_norm amp2_norm]
132
133 Y_aug = hcat(repeat([1.0,0,0], 1,samples),
134             repeat([0,1.0,0], 1,samples),
135             repeat([0,0,1.0], 1,samples))
136
137
138 #####
139 # TRAIN NETWORK #
140 #####
141
142
143 W1,b1,W2,b2 = train(X_aug, Y_aug)
144
145
146 #####
147 # TEST ON REAL DATA #
148 #####
149
150 println("\nTesting real samples (never seen in training):")
151
152 classes = ["REST", "COLD", "MAX"]
153 real-samples = [log10.(amp0) log10.(amp1) log10.(amp2)]
154
155 for i in 1:3
156     p = predict(W1,b1,W2,b2, real-samples[:,i])
157     println("Real sample $i = $(classes[i]) : prediction = $p")
158 end

```

A.3 Train NN

```

1
2
3 # Train NN to recognize state of fan
4 using CSV, DataFrames
5 using Plots
6 using Printf
7 using Statistics
8 gr()
9
10 cd(@_DIR_)
11
12 #####
13 # DATA AUGMENTATION FUNCTION #
14 #####
15
16 function augment-sample(x, n::Int=500; noise-frac=0.1)
17     x_vec = vec(x)
18     L = length(x_vec)
19     out = zeros(L, n)
20     for i in 1:n
21         out[:, i] = x_vec .+ noise-frac * abs.(randn(L))
22     end
23     return out
24 end
25
26
27 #####
28 # TRAINING FUNCTION #
29 #####
30
31 function train(X.mat, Y.mat)
32     nInput, m = size(X.mat)
33     nHidden = 20
34     nOutput = 3
35
36     W1 = 0.01 .* randn(nHidden, nInput)
37     b1 = zeros(nHidden, 1)
38     W2 = 0.01 .* randn(nOutput, nHidden)
39     b2 = zeros(nOutput, 1)
40
41     lr = 0.1
42     epochs = 2000
43     loss_history = zeros(epochs)
44
45     for epoch in 1:epochs
46
47         ##### FORWARD #####
48         Z1 = W1 * X.mat .+ b1
49         A1 = tanh.(Z1)
50
51         Z2 = W2 * A1 .+ b2
52         expZ = exp.(Z2 .- maximum(Z2, dims=1))
53         A2 = expZ ./ sum(expZ, dims=1)
54
55         ##### LOSS #####
56         loss = -sum(Y.mat .* log.(A2))
57         loss_history[epoch] = loss
58
59         ##### BACKPROP #####
60         m = size(X.mat, 2)
61
62         dZ2 = (A2 .- Y.mat) ./ m
63         dW2 = dZ2 * A1'
64         db2 = sum(dZ2, dims=2)
65
66         dA1 = W2' * dZ2
67         dZ1 = dA1 .* (1 .- A1.^2)
68
69         dW1 = dZ1 * X.mat'
70         db1 = sum(dZ1, dims=2)
71
72         ##### UPDATE #####
73         W1 .-= lr .* dW1
74         b1 .-= lr .* db1
75         W2 .-= lr .* dW2
76         b2 .-= lr .* db2
77
78         if epoch % 100 == 0
79             @printf("Epoch %d Loss = %.4f\n", epoch, loss)

```

A.4 Payload Formatter

```
1
2 function decodeUplink(input) {
3   const bytes = input.bytes;
4
5   // ---- uptime (uint32 big-endian) ----
6   const uptime =
7     (bytes[0] << 24) |
8     (bytes[1] << 16) |
9     (bytes[2] << 8) |
10    bytes[3];
11
12   // ---- temperature (float32 little-endian) ----
13   const buf = new ArrayBuffer(4);
14   const view = new DataView(buf);
15   view.setUint8(0, bytes[4]);
16   view.setUint8(1, bytes[5]);
17   view.setUint8(2, bytes[6]);
18   view.setUint8(3, bytes[7]);
19   const temperature = view.getFloat32(0, true);
20
21   // ---- prediction class ----
22   const class_id = bytes[8];
23
24   let class_name = "UNKNOWN";
25   if (class_id === 0) class_name = "REST";
26   if (class_id === 1) class_name = "COLD";
27   if (class_id === 2) class_name = "MAX";
28
29   return {
30     data: {
31       uptime-seconds: uptime,
32       temperature_c: temperature,
33       class_id: class_id,
34       class_name: class_name
35     }
36   };
37 }
```